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CORPORATE IDENTITY MANAGEMENT: A PANACEA FOR ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF HOTELS IN RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to investigate the relationship between corporate identity management and organizational performance of hotels in Rivers State. Drawing from its theoretical baseline, the study was anchored on resource-based theory and relational-view theory. Cross-sectional survey design was used in accessing the study's subjects. The population of the study comprised of staff of four-star hotels in Rivers State. Data obtained through this process were analyzed and a total of 5 hypotheses were tested using Regression Analysis. Findings from these tests revealed a positive and significant correlation between the dimensions of corporate identity management (corporate reputation and corporate communication) and the measures of organizational performance (organisational growth and marketing effectiveness). The study concluded that corporate identity management has been confirmed to be reliable management tool to help improve organizational performance. Based on the conclusion, the study therefore recommended that management of 4-star hotels to in building and maintain their identity, management are encouraged to design and implement services that are appealing to stakeholders and the public. This will bring about stakeholders' endorsement and reputation for the banks. In order to enhance organisational performance, management of 4-star hotels are expected to disseminate vital information about the organization's corporate existence and value propositions on one hand, and to also coordinate inter-departmental flow of information in order to ensure that the corporate marketing strategies are understood and implemented by every employee of the organization.

KEYWORDS

Corporate Identity Management, Corporate Communication, Marketing Effectiveness.

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INTRODUCTION

The global hospitality has witnessed monumental gains due to its strong appetite for growth, propelled by renewed investor confidence, innovativeness, global events, global partnership and collaboration, competitiveness, etc. Available records from the United Nation Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2020), indicates that global tourism sector had created over \$2 trillion US businesses, accounting for 11.3% of world consumption in 1997. Its direct contribution to GDP in 2017 was USD2, 306 billion (3.1% of GDP). This is forecasted to rise by 3.8% to USD2, 394.2 billion in 2018 (UNCTAD, 2020). It may not be far from the truth to mention that the hospitality industry is the livewire of tourism activities at all levels. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020), between 70% and 75% of international tourists' expenditure goes to hospitality services on annual basis. This substantiates the importance of the sector to tourism which hotel organizations play a prominent role. In Nigeria, there is no gainsaying to deny the fact that the hospitality sector has demonstrated tremendous growth especially within the last decade leading to the emergence of top-notch hotels, fast-food restaurant, night clubs, yacht cruise lines, event centres, and other entertainment activities. Given this trend of event, Kinetic Consulting (2020) reported that the sector contributed over 48.8% of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and alone, employed over 1.6% of Nigerians in 2016. Interestingly, these contributions has showed positive result in the country's economy thereby helping to redefine and add value to the hospitality industry.

In today's volatile, unpredictable and unstable business environment, owners and strategists of hotels in Nigeria have realised the strategic importance of building and managing the identity of the corporation. In line with this, Victor, DagogoandOdunayo (2018) are of the view that managers with huge experience in the hospitality business know that employing identity management strategy is key to enhancing organisation performance. As a result, superior performance reached through corporate identity management practices such as corporate reputation, corporate communication and cooperate culture, helps hotels organisations build competitive advantage, and secure the market leadership (Nwosu, 2018).

In addition, a number of researchers have argued that corporate identity as an organization's presentation of itself to its various stakeholders and the way it distinguishes itself from similar and/or competitive organizations. These presentations would include the activities of designing logos, training the employees, decorating interior, corporate culture, and even brand equity, etc (Kiriakidou& Millward, 2000). Topalian (2003) stated that corporate identity management is the articulation of what an organization is, what it stands for, what it does and how it goes about its business. A successful identity enables the firm increase productivity while improving its image and public trust. Employees should understand and adopt the corporate identity in such ways as to bring it to life for themselves and those they serve and they will make it easy for others to recognize the organization and identify with it (Topalian, 2003).

The conceptual definition of corporate identity management is a firm's strategically planned and purposeful presentation of itself in order to gain a positive corporate image in the minds of the public. A corporate identity is established in order to gain a favourable corporate reputation over time (Allesandri, 2001). The operational definition of corporate identity management refers to all the observable and measurable elements of a firm's identity manifesting in its comprehensive visual presentation of itself, including its name, logo, tagline, colour palette and architecture. Corporate

identity also includes the firm's public behaviour, including its reception of employees, customers, shareholders and suppliers (Allesandri, 2001).

Corporate identity management is of crucial importance for an organization that strives to achieve success. By clear and structured management, organizations are able to create an adaptable corporate identity, which in this case means an identity that can manage to survive the environmental changes that has been going on the past decades (Balmer & Gray, 2001). Kiriakidou and Millward (2000) express the same kind of need for corporate identity management. They argue that clear and good management will erase the discrepancy that may occur within an organization, when employees do not support the desired corporate identity. This is mostly a cause of poor communication within the organization, which creates uncertainty about the identity (Kiriakidou & Millward, 2000). The corporate name, logo and tagline are, as written above, collectively typically referred to as a part of an organization's corporate identity. The regular exposures of this corporate identity in all forms of marketing and advertising are believed to contribute to the public's learning about the organization. Over time, the corporate identity affects the public's perception of the organization (Alessandri, 2001). A corporate identity should be "lived" in order to be successful. It should be meaningful and understandable by employees and other stakeholders (Topalian, 2003).

Plethora of research works have been carried out in the area of corporate identity management. Fombrum & Van Riel (2004) highlighted corporate image and corporate communication as an effective corporate identity management dimensions. More so, Bartkowski, Walsh & Beatty (2011) highlighted corporate reputation, organizational communication and corporate culture as components of corporate identity management. Bloomenthal (2019) and Yu, Zhang, Kim, Chen, Henderson, Min and Huang (2014) investigated the impact of corporate identity management on business success. The authors used employee productivity, market expansion and profitability as measures of business success. In view of the above studies and other related ones, this research deviated from extant studies by combining corporate reputation, corporate communication and corporate culture as dimensions of corporate identity management with a view to examining their relationship with the measures of organisational performance such as organisational growth, employee productivity and marketing effectiveness. This research further deviated from extant researches by introducing corporate image as a moderating variable in to our framework in order to examine its moderating effect on the relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performance as it relates to hotels in Rivers State. Thus, this research was set out to investigate the relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, one of the main objectives of many hotels is to initiate strategies that would help improve organizational performance. Activities and operations of hotels in recent years have put the industry in a bad light; hence, the issue of reputation and image. In fact, many see hotels as places where individuals orchestrate deviant activities, of which often times are protected by hotel management in return for continuous patronage and loyalty. Again the issue of consistency in quality service delivery has brought about the issue of trust; in terms of having the capacity to consistently deliver superior value over time. According to Small and Medium Enterprises & Development Agency in Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2020), most small and medium hotels find it difficult to continuously improve performance especially after one year from the start of operation. This is due to some myriad challenges, which includes, poor inter-personal communication, poor security infrastructure, decline in efficiency rates, poor quality control and customer service, little or no standardisation in operations,

inconsistent service policies, slower intelligence sharing, high operation costs and an overall decline of quality service delivery (SMEDAN, 2020). The above issues has had a negative impact on hotels ability to improve productivity, compete favourable among rivals, expand market share, just to mention but a few. Nevertheless, a number of strategies such as reduction of room rates and other beverage prices, recruitment of new personnel (especially at the managerial and supervisory level), etc; however, the problem seems to persist (Buchaska, Chmielewski & Doczeskalska, 2015).

In view of these challenges, the question begs as to whether corporate identity management is the solution. Specifically, can effective corporate identity management leads to improved organisational performance? In providing an interim answer to the above question, studies have suggested that with this increased competition, hotels are turning to corporate identity management as a source of competitive advantage which if well managed may impact positively on business success (Kim, Jeon, Jung, Lu & Jones, 2011; Balmer & Gray, 2001). In this regard, Kim et al. (2011), argued that changes in customer needs and expectations of service offerings has modified and changed how customers construct their image of hotels. This is arguably one of the main reason why hotels today have to build a clear corporate identity and a strategy for a strong corporate communication and reputation. The importance of corporate communication cannot be neglected since it forms the conjunction between an organization's corporate identity and its image in the minds of people. In this research, we want to investigate the nature of relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Resource Based Theory (RBT): The Research Based Theory (RBT) has its origins in strategic management. RBT is a central concept in understanding how entrepreneurial firms identify and acquire resources to achieve competitive advantage (Brown, Davidsson & Wiklund, 2001). According to RBT, resources can be combined or developed over time to generate unique capabilities that increase competitive advantage (Amit & Shoemaker, 1993). Schumpeter (1934) points to the link between RBT and entrepreneurship and defines entrepreneurship as the activity associated with innovatively combining resources into something that the market identifies as new. The RBT deals with competitive advantages related to the firm's possession of heterogeneous resources (financial, physical, human, technological, organizational, and reputational) and capabilities (combination of two or more resources) (Miller & Ross, 2003). These resources and capabilities constitute the core competence of the particular firm and serve ultimately as its source of competitive advantage. The static stream of research focuses on attributes that contribute to the heterogeneity of resources and capabilities. Four barriers may prevent competitors from imitating a firm's resources and capabilities: durability, transparency, transferability and replicability (Miller & Ross, 2003).

These attributes may also apply to inter-organizational arrangements (Jap, 2001). The more dynamic aspects of the RBT consider a firm's core competence to be its ability to react quickly to situational changes and build further competencies (Miller & Ross, 2003) or dynamic capabilities (Brown et al., 2001). Hence, a firm's competitiveness is associated with the configuration of resources and capabilities as the markets evolve. However, inter-organizational relationships may also facilitate and advance the learning processes of individual may not only be explained in terms of productivity or operational measures, but also in terms of the opportunity to access another firm's core competencies through cooperative arrangements as an alternative to building such competencies in-house. According to Hart (1995), RBT suggests that the identification and implementation of a firm's internal strategic resources contributes to the firm's ability to develop and maintain competitive

advantage that allow it achieve stated goals and objectives. Because the resources of firms vary, RBT attempts to explain how firms identify strategic resources that enables them outpace competitors by building strategically sound offerings for their target markets (Hart, 1995).

Relational View Theory:The Relational View Theory (RVT) is another theory that is considered suitable for this work. The RVT is considered very useful because it helped in solving some of the controversies or limitations surrounding the RBV. Basically, the RVT propounded by Dyer and Singh (1998) has its roots primarily in the RBV. According to the scholar, because the exchange in networks of inter-organizational relation will result to a higher value that explains a higher firm performance; RVT has assisted in recognizing both the internal and external strategic resources which RBV fails to do. This research understands that firm heterogeneity is an important element in achieving differentiated performance. However, the RBV was incapable of explaining how firms develop competitive advantage in networked environments where group of firms maintain frequent and multiple collaborative relationship with alliance partners (Lavie, 2006). The authors have confirmed these constraints by evaluating the limitations of the RBV in explaining competitive advantage in networked environment. The author further opined that the RV was therefore developed in order to eliminate the barriers where the RBV could not reach.

The RV emerged due to increasing for value by customers and other key stakeholders within the supply chain. Therefore, joint efforts among stakeholders are strategically combined to increase efficiency and enhance supply chain performance (Dyer & Singh, 1998). The connectedness and increased tendency to collaborate among logistical firms gave birth to the RV theory. Dollinger, Li & Mooney (2019) in their view of RVT, argued that when internal strategic resources are strategically combined with collaborative alliances with suppliers, distributors, financiers, customer groups etc; then the magnitude of the overall performance individual stakeholder may be unimaginable.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework on Corporate Identity Management and Organisational Performance

Source: Research Desk, 2023; as adapted from Fombrum and Van Riel, 2004;Bartikowski, Walsh& Beatty, 2011;Yu, Zhang, Kim, Chen, Henderson, Min and Huang,2014.

Concept of Corporate Identity Management

Arrays of corporate identity management definitions have been advanced in the literature. Reaching a consensus of opinion with regard to defining corporate identity management has proven a challenging task. Earlier scholars' definitions tended to focus on the visual aspects of corporate identity. For instance Hatch & Schultz's (2008) defined corporate identity management as the logo or brand image of a company and all other visual manifestations of the identity of a company. Dowling (1994) considered the concept as the symbols; a self-presentation of an organization, rooted in the behaviour of individual organizational members, expressing the organization's sameness over time, continuity and distinctiveness. Gray & Balmer (1998) define the construct as the reality and uniqueness of the organization.

Fombrun (1996) describes corporate identity management as the features of the company that appear to be central and enduring to employees. Corporate identity management consists of both desired identity and actual identity, where the former refers to what the organization wants internal stakeholders to know or think about the firm while the latter refers to what internal stakeholders actually know or think about the firm (Walker, 2010). Corporate identity is seen to be mental pictures of an organization. And the totality of these mental picture characteristics is what is referred to corporate identity. Corporate Identity Management entails transmission of what the organization is and what it stands for to internal and external stakeholders through strategically planned visual identity, corporate values, reputation, communication and behaviour hence involve managing factors that impact the favourability of a corporation's identity. It also focuses on the important role of employees and senior management given their significant role in the process of managing corporate identity.

Organizational Performance

A good number of authors have advanced discussions on organizational performance (Dhillon & Vachhrajani, 2012). In fact, Organizational performance is arguably the most widely use dependent variable in management research literature today yet at the same time remains one of the vaguest and loosely defined concepts. However, it is important to distinguish between performance and organizational performance. Performance is a set of financial and non-financial indices that explains information on the extent of achievement of results (Dhillon & Vachhrajani, 2012). On the other hand, organizational performance is defined as an organization's ability to attain its objectives by using resources at its disposal in an efficient and effective way. According to Lambe, (2014), organizational performance refers to the ability of an enterprise to achieve objectives that reflects high profit, quality of product, large market share, good financial results, and survival at predetermined time using relevant strategies and actions. Lee and Bruold (2003) mentioned that organizational performance is a reflection of productivity of personnel of an organization measured in terms of revenue, profit, growth, development and expansion of the organization. A major objective of hotel management is profit maximization and shareholders' maximization epitomizing corporate performance. It is imperative to mention that this study used corporate growth and marketing effectiveness as measures of corporate performance.

Corporate Identity Management and Organizational Performance

The nexus between corporate identity management and organisational has been noted and documented in the literature. Balmer and gray (2003) had observed that corporate identity management contributes to a favorable image and reputation, inclination to use organizations products and services, to work for the organization and to speak well about it. Similarly, Balmer and Gray (2001) in their study, claimed that firms are better prepared if they manage their corporate identity towards external environmental influences that can drastically change the conditions under which they operate. Christensen and Askegaard (2001) concur noting that a strong identity is beneficial to an

organization as it adds value to increasingly similar products; ensures consumer confidence and loyalty; stimulates investments; attracts high-quality personnel; and nurtures employee motivation.

Corporate Reputation and Organisational Performance

A growing body of literature has led to many alternative definitions of corporate reputation. For Gotsiand Wilson (2001), corporate reputation should be viewed as ‘a stakeholder’s overall evaluation of a company over time’. Reputation is an important intangible asset for organizations of any kind. Marken (2002) defined corporate reputation as assets that include ‘quality of products and services, ability to innovate, value as long-term investment, financial stability, ability to attract, develop, retain talent; use of corporate assets, and quality of management.

Kinoti (2012) had focused on green marketing practices, corporate image, organizational characteristics and performance of ISO certified organizations and concluded that green marketing practices influence performance while corporate image intervened and organizational characteristics moderated the relationship. Owino (2013) focused on Service Quality and Corporate Image on Customer Satisfaction among University students in Kenya and concluded that there exists a significant difference in the dimensions of service quality between public and private university students. Njeru (2013) analyzed the relationship between market orientation and performance of tour firms in Kenya and found that market orientation influences performance. Ndungu (2013) focused on Quality drivers, managerial focus, customer perception and satisfaction in large flour mills in Nairobi Kenya. We therefore hypothesize as follows:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between corporate reputation and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between corporate reputation and employee marketing performance of hotels in Rivers State.

Corporate Communication and Organisational Performance

Corporate communication has been defined as the process by which information is exchanged and understood by two or more people, usually with the intent to motivate or influence behaviour (Daft, 1997). It is important to notice that this definition of communication stresses its intent - a purpose that may go beyond just transferring information. The sender has the intent to influence the receiver to do what the sender wants (Kelly, 2000). Corporate communication stakeholders are divided into two, which are; internal (employees, shareholder, manager and etc.) and external (agencies, channel partners, media, government and general public). Corporate communication employs dividing lines between internal and external communication with its very own research traditions (Thiessen & Inghoff, 2011). This is an example of internal communication, i.e. Communication between different levels of an organization. Communication is a “bridge” to link and direct all the levels of an organization in achieving organization objective.

Goodman (2004) argues that corporate communication is a strategic tool in developing a competitive advantage. A study by Convey (2004) on the significance of corporate communication on levels of staff commitment to company objectives found that no more than one in three employees knew what the organization was trying to achieve and why, and just one in five were excited about these objectives. Not surprising then, just one in ten employees felt that the organization expected staff members to take responsibility for the results of company operations. The study implies that organizational performance is adversely affected by inadequate communication and poor management, which together create a motivating organizational culture. Fenton & Langley (2011) who examined the effect of corporate communication on consumer purchase behaviour, found that corporate communication has a strong and positive effect on customer satisfaction and word-of-mouth referral. According to the findings of Cooren et al. (2011), corporate communication was confirmed to

significantly relate to customer loyalty and repeat purchase. Corporate communication is vital to a firm and if they are well managed, they are likely to enhance the firm's competitive advantage through the organizational corporate image. We therefore hypothesize as follows:

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between corporate communication and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between corporate communication and marketing effectiveness of hotels in Rivers State.

Corporate Culture and Organisational Performance

Early studies have indicated that there exist relationship between organizational culture and its performance. Magee (2002) in this very point argued that organizational culture is inherently connected to organizational practices; therefore organizational performance is conditional on organizational culture. According to Hellriegel and Slocum (2009), organizational culture can enhance performance in a large scale if it can be understood that what sustains a culture. According to these authors the culture of an organization allows the employees to be acquainted with both the firm's history as well as current methods of operation and this specific detection endows the employees with guidance about expected and acceptable future organizational behaviors and norms.

Some theoretical models assert that the effective human resource system of an organization is based on supporting values and then these systems, in turn, create a positive impact on employee attitudes and behavior, which facilitate organization's performance (Ferris et al., 1998). Mercer and Bilson (1985) also point out the correlation between organizational culture and employees' performance; and this employees' performance then translated into organizational outcomes such as customer satisfaction (Schmidt, Shull, & Schmitt, 2001). Hence, the hypothesis below:

H₀₅: Corporate image does not significantly moderate the relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State.

Empirical Review

Adebayo, (2017) examined the effect of corporate brand identity management and organisational performance among higher educational institutions in south western Nigeria. The stratified random sampling technique was used to select respondents from the selected institutions. A well-structured self-administered questionnaire was used as the main tool for data collection. The population of the study was 3234 and based on Krejcie and Morgan Research Sample size table, 356 questionnaires were administered randomly to faculties and staff drawn from a private and Federal University, while 334 copies of the questionnaires were valid and retrieved which shows 93.82% rate of response used for the analysis. Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23) was used to analyse the Data collated using regression and correlation analysis. Findings from the study showed that, there is a relationship between Human resource initiatives and employees' affective commitment at ($r=0.745$ and $R^2= .555$) which implies that, Human resource initiatives accounts for 55.5% of variation on employees' affective commitment. The study recommended that the strategic management should ensure appropriate corporate brand identity management strategies (Human Resource Initiatives, Corporate Visual, Identity, Advertising/On-line Marketing, Employee/Client Focus, and Brand Personality) that will enhance the corporate brand of their organization. Also in driving the overall performance of the brand, organisations are to be mindful of building the right brand image which ensures the development of cross-functional ties between the marketing and publicity department in conjunction with the human resource department to foster the corporate brand

Tabitha (2019) the broad objective of the study was to determine the influence of Corporate Identity Management (CIM) practices, Organizational Characteristics and Corporate Image on Brand Performance of Kenyan Universities. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was used. Primary data

were collected from key informants using semi-structured questionnaires. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, inferential statistics and regression analysis. The results of the study revealed a statistically significant relationship between corporate identity management practices and brand performance which was mediated by Corporate Image and moderated by Organizational Characteristics. Similarly, the results revealed a statistically significant relationship between Organizational characteristics and brand performance. The results showed that CIM practices had a statistically significant relationship on corporate image. Corporate image also had a statistically significant influence on brand performance.

Adebayo, Kehinde, Ogunnaike, Olaoye and Adesanya (2019) investigated the effects of corporate brand identity on service quality in selected higher educational institutions. It explores the possible effects of online marketing on service quality and determines the influence of corporate visual identity on brand performance. A federal and a private university in Nigeria have been selected for this study and 356 copies of questionnaire are administered randomly to members of faculty and staff of these universities. 334 copies of the questionnaire are valid at 93.82% response rate, and these are used for the analysis. The findings indicate that the top management of organisations should ensure the adoption of corporate brand identity management for resilience in their performance.

Methodology

This research adopted the cross-sectional survey design on the basis that the research involved selecting samples of elements from the population of interest measurable at a particular point in time. Again, because the phenomenon is not within the control of the researcher, and that the research is for academic purposes and is time-bound; hence, this research design was found suitable for this research. Basically, the population of this study was limited to four-star hotels in Rivers State, due to the fact that currently, there is no five-star hotel in the state. According to the Hotel Association of Nigeria (HAN, 2023), there are a total of twelve (12) Four-Star hotels in Rivers State. The table below shows the various hotels and their addresses.

Table 1 List of Four-Star Hotels in Rivers State

S/N	NAME	ADDRESS
1	Presidential Hotel	No. 5141 Aba road, by Rumuola, GRA Phase II, Port Harcourt.
2	Echelen Heights Hotel	No. 73 Ken Saro-Wiwa road, Port Harcourt.
3	Golden Tulip Hotel	1C Evo Crescent, GRA Phase II, Port Harcourt.
4	Novotel Hotel	No. 3 Stadium road, Rumuomasi, Port Harcourt.
5	Le Meridien Hotels	No. 45 Tombia street Phase II, GRA Port Harcourt.
6	Beverly Hills Hotels	130, Woji Road, GRA Phase II, Port Harcourt.
7	Habitat Hotel	No. 5 Harbitat Drive, Rumualaogu, Choba Road, PH.
8	Swiss International Mabisel	No. 9 Mabisel Avenue, Off Peter Odili Road, Port Harcourt.
9	Limewood Hotels	Plot F, 1B Abacha Road, GRA Phase III.
10	Swiss Spirit	No. 79 Ken Saro-Wiwa Road, Rumuola, Port Harcourt.
11	Genesis Raventon	No 7 Brookstone Close, Professor Abowei Street, New GRA, Port Harcourt.
12	Best Western Hotels	Plot F35 Woke Street, Off Sani Abacha Road, GRA III Port Harcourt.

Source: HAN (2023)

It is pertinent to state that this research targeted designated positions of each of the hotels. Positions that were involved include; general managers, assistant managers, human resource managers,

marketing manager, operations manager, procurement manager, food & beverage manager, accountant/auditor, and store officers. These nine (9) top positions across the twelve (12) hotels constituted the research target population. Based on the above analysis, the research has a total of one hundred and eight (108) senior staff that were accessed in this research. In addition, based on the target population size (108), which is manageable, there was no need for drawing samples. Hence, the researcher approached/contacted personnel occupying those positions of interest with copies of the questionnaire in the above listed hotels.

Data for this study were obtained from primary and secondary sources. Primary data include information obtained from respondents using specially designed research questionnaire. Responses to the questionnaire were scaled on a five-point Likert-type continuum. The questionnaire was administered by hand with the help of a research assistant. Due to the distance between the locations of these hotels, the respondents were given time within which to fill out the questionnaire. Within the time, follow-up visits on the respondents or reminders were sent to contact persons in each of the hotels. On the other hand, secondary data were sourced through textbooks, journal articles, industry publications, and unpublished sources such as past researches in related areas.

More so, to validate the research instrument, the researcher ensured that the structured questionnaire was subjected to the combination of face and content validity. Face validity judges at the face value the appropriateness of the measuring instrument. Content validity is the extent to which the items of an instrument are representative of the content and behaviour specified by the theoretical content being measured. Also, a proper restructuring of the questionnaire and the conduct of a pre-test of every question contained in the questionnaire was carried out to ensure that they are valid. Response validity was obtained by re-contacting individual respondents whose responses have appeared unclear, unusual or inconsistent.

This study investigated the nature and extent of relationship between two variables; at the first level of analyses which is descriptive in nature, Excel version 2016 was used to analyse the demographic characteristics of respondents. Subsequently, the study adopted Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Co-efficient data analysis technique at the secondary level of analysis. It was set out to check the extent to which corporate identity management correlates organisational performance. Similarly, Partial Correlation Coefficient was used to measure the moderating effect of corporate image with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0.

The consistency and validation of the research instrument was examined through a pilot study in order to scrutinize the validity/reliability of the HRSPCA instruments. The pilot study involved 30 employees of hotels that were purposively selected from the population. Furthermore, Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA) were conducted in validating statement items on all the studied variables and to determine the construct validity of the research instruments. The results of the CFA were provided below:

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Table 2: Measurement Model: Reliability and Validity for CR, CC, OG, ME and CI

Construct	Item	Loading	CR	AVE	A
CR	CR1	0.756			
CR	CR2	0.801	0.876	0.639	0.811
CR	CR3	0.822			
CR	CR4	0.818			
CC	CC1	0.768			

CC	CC2	0.874	0.873	0.635	0.858
CC	CC3	0.697			
OG	OG1	0.878			
OG	OG2	0.733	0.799	0.514	0.773
OG	OG3	0.759			
OG	OG4	0.412			
ME	MEO1	0.866			
ME	MEO2	0.854	0.920	0.741	0.885
ME	MEO3	0.888			
ME	MEO4	0.836			
CI	CI1	0.895			
CI	CI2	0.775	0.890	0.640	0.802
CI	CI3	0.717			
CI	CI4	0.801			

Source: SMARTPLS Result Output, 2023.

As evidenced in Table 2, this research witnessed all the observed variables (statement items) loaded was high against their elemental factors (latent variables), owing to factor loadings ranging from 0.412 to 0.895. These values are all above the suggested minimum of 0.6, implying that they are valid measures of their latent factors. Also, for all cases, CR, AVE and Cronbach Alpha (α) are higher than their suggested threshold values of 0.7 respectively. All these imply that our data achieve convergent validity. For discriminant validity, we follow the usual procedure by comparing the Cronbach Alpha (α) with the pairwise correlation coefficient between the constructs. In all, our measurement analysis shows that corporate reputation, corporate communication, organisational growth, marketing effectiveness and cooperate image are all objectively and validly measured by their respective statement items contained in our research instrument.

Results and Discussion

Results

Questionnaire Distribution Rate

Table 3 Questionnaire Distribution

Details	Questionnaire	Percentage (%)
Distributed	108	100
Returned	102	94
Not Returned	6	6
Returned completed	94	87
Returned incomplete	8	7

From the above table, a total of 108 copies of questionnaire were distributed, however, only 102 copies representing 94% were retrieved, hence, 6 copies representing 6% were not returned. More so, out of the number of copies returned, only 94 copies representing 87%, were completely field and found useful for the study. Only 8 copies were discarded.

Hypotheses Testing

Table 4: Regression Analysis showing the relationship between corporate reputation (CR), corporate communication (CC) and organisational growth (OG)

	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Unstandardized Coefficients (Beta)	T	Sig.	VIF
	.742 ^a	.551	.653	63.318			.000	.532
Constant					4.055	-1.136		
Corporate Reputation					.841	2.104	.000	
Corporate Communication					.722	2.713	.000	

Dependent Variable: Organisational Growth

Regression line

$Y = a + bX_1 + bX_2$:Where:

Organisational Growth = 4.055+[(0.841CR) + (0.722CC)]

R = 0.742; R² = 0.551; F_{2, 94}=63.318; P-value = 0.000

The results above indicated R=0.742, R²=0.551 which is equal to 55.1% and this is the explanatory power of the model as it is used. It means that only 55.1% variation can be explained by factors within the model used for the study and the remaining 44.9% can only be explained by other external quantitative and qualitative factors of the model used for the study. The f-ratio (F_{2, 94}=63.318) showed significant effects in existence and this revealed the appropriateness of the model used for the study. For beta coefficient, corporate reputation had the highest contribution value of 0.841 at 0.000 probability value, meaning it is positively significant while corporate communication came second with 0.722 contribution value at p-value of 0.000. Also, the p-value<0.05 for the two dimensions of predictor as showed in Table 4. These results means that the null hypotheses (H₀₁ and H₀₃) were rejected as regard the cost leadership.

Table 5: Regression Analysis showing the relationship between corporate reputation (CR), corporate communication (CC) and marketing effectiveness (ME)

	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Unstandardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.	VIF
	.763 ^a	.582	.720	92.514			.000	.601
Constant					7.187	2.172		
Corporate Reputation					.251	2.226	.000	
Corporate Communication					.581	2.372	.000	

Dependent Variable: Marketing Effectiveness

Regression line

$Y = a + bX_1 + bX_2$:Where:

Marketing Effectiveness = 7.187+[(0.251CR) + (0.581CC)]

R = 0.763; R² = 0.582; F_{2, 94}=92.514; P-value = 0.000

The results above indicated $R=0.763$, $R^2=0.582$ which is equal to 58.2% and this is the explanatory power of the model as it is used. It means that only 58.2% variation can be explained by factors within the model used for the study and the remaining 41.8% can only be explained by other external quantitative and qualitative factors of the model used for the study. The F-ratio ($F_{2, 94}=92.514$) showed significant effects in existence and this revealed the appropriateness of the model used for the study. For beta coefficient, corporate communication had the highest contribution value of 0.581 at 0.000 probability value while corporate reputation came second with 0.251 contribution value at p-value of 0.000. Also, the $p\text{-value}<0.05$ for the two dimensions of predictor as showed in Table 5. These results means that the null hypotheses (H_{02} and H_{04}) were rejected as regard word of mouth.

Test of Hypothesis using Partial Correlation

H₀₅: Corporate image does not significantly moderate the relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State.

Table 6: Partial correlation analysis showing the influence of corporate image on the relationship between corporate reputation management and organisational performance

Partial Corr.

Correlations

Control Variables				Corporate Identity Management	Organisational Performance
Corporate Image	Corporate Management	Identity Correlation	(2-tailed)	1.000	.573
		Significance		.	.003
		Df		0	94
Organisational Performance	Corporate Management	Identity Correlation	(2-tailed)	.573	1.000
		Significance		.002	.
		Df		94	0

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Decision: Table6 explained the moderating influence of corporate image on the relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performanceof hotels in Rivers State. The result revealed that a moderate but positive significant relationship exist between corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State and the probability value (P-value) was less than the confidence level of 0.05, meaning that the assertion stated in the hypothesis was rejected ($r=0.573$, $Pv=0.002<0.05$). Corporate image on the other hand also had a moderate but positive relationship with corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State at 0.611. Therefore, we accept the assertion that there is a moderating influence of corporate image on the significant relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performanceof hotels in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

There is a significant relationship between corporate reputation and organisational performance

The first hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between corporate reputation and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State. The R value 0.742 shows a significant relationship between corporate reputation and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State. The value of path coefficient between corporate reputation and organisational growth was measured as 0.841. The t-value is 2.104 which is greater than critical value of 1.96 and the p-value of 0.000 which is also significant and less than the threshold value of 0.05 proved the significance of this path. These statistics provided sufficient evidence to reject hypothesis H_{01} and also determined that there is a significant positive relationship between corporate reputation and organisational growth. From our analysis, the null hypothesis was rejected at 5% significance level, implying that corporate reputation and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State.

The second hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between corporate reputation and marketing effectiveness of hotels in Rivers State. The R value 0.763 shows a significant relationship between corporate reputation and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State. The value of path coefficient between corporate reputation and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State was measured as 0.251. The t-value is 2.226 which is greater than critical value of 1.96 and the p-value of 0.000 which is also significant and less than the threshold value of 0.05 proved the significance of this path. These statistics provided sufficient evidence to reject hypothesis H_{02} and also determined that there is a significant positive relationship between corporate reputation and marketing effectiveness. From our analysis, the null hypothesis was rejected at 5% significance level, implying that corporate reputation have significant impact on marketing effectiveness of hotels in Rivers State.

The above results were in agreement with the study of Abd-El-Salam et al. (2013) work on the impact of corporate image and reputation on service quality, customer satisfaction and organisational growth where survey data was collected from 650 customers of an international service company showed that there was a significant positive relationship between corporate image and reputation and customer loyalty which ultimately impacts on an organization's performance. In their findings, corporate reputation was found to have more significant impact on firm performance than corporate image has on customer loyalty.

There is a significant relationship between corporate communication and organisational performance

The third hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between corporate communication and organisational growth in hotels in Rivers State. The R value 0.742 shows a significant relationship between corporate communication and organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State. The value of path coefficient between corporate communication and organisational growth was measured as 0.722. The t-value is 2.713 which is greater than critical value of 1.96 and the p-value of 0.000 which is also significant and less than the threshold value of 0.05 proved the significance of this path. These statistics provided sufficient evidence to reject hypothesis H_{03} and also determined that there is a significant positive relationship between corporate communication and organisational growth. From our analysis, the null hypothesis was rejected at 5% significance level, implying that corporate communication has significant impact on organisational growth of hotels in Rivers State.

The fourth hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between corporate communication and marketing effectiveness of hotels in Rivers State. The R value 0.763 shows a significant relationship between corporate communications has significant impact on marketing effectiveness of hotels in Rivers State. The value of path coefficient between corporate communication and marketing effectiveness was measured as 0.581. The t-value is 2.372 which is greater than critical value of 1.96

and the p-value of 0.000 which is also significant and less than the threshold value of 0.05 proved the significance of this path. These statistics provided sufficient evidence to reject hypothesis H_{04} and also determined that there is a significant positive relationship between corporate communication and marketing effectiveness. From our analysis, the null hypothesis was rejected at 5% significance level, implying that corporate communication and marketing effectiveness of hotels in Rivers State. These findings were consistent with the findings of Fenton & Langley (2011), who examined the effect of corporate communication on consumer purchase behaviour. The authors found that corporate communication has a strong and positive effect on customer satisfaction and word-of-mouth referral. According to the findings of Coorenet al. (2011), corporate communication was confirmed to significantly relate to customer loyalty and repeat purchase.

Corporate image does not significantly moderate the relationship between corporate identity management and organisational performance

Hypothesis five (H_{05}), the extent of the influence of corporate image on corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State. This hypothesis sought to examine the moderating influence of corporate image on the association between corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State. The Partial correlation was used in testing the influence of the corporate image on corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State indicated that the organizational factor impact has significant influence on corporate identity management and organisational performance of hotels in Rivers State.

Conclusions

It is no longer news as to the imperativeness of managing what people have come to know about an organization and may want to associate themselves with the brand. Identity management is known to be a complex phenomenon, yet corporate strategists have always strive to make it as simple as possible in order to manage its complexity and convert it to a tool that puts the organization ahead of others in terms of competitiveness. Corporate identity management has been further confirmed to be a strategic machinery to improving employee productivity and organisational growth. It was revealed that organizations that have good reputations are able to attract stakeholders' endorsement which lead to positive marketing effectiveness. Organizations who customers hold on high esteem are the ones with high perceived value due to their long-held service reputation. A favourable corporate reputation gives a firm a better competitive advantage and also enhances organisational performance.

Corporate identity is formed by an organization's history in the mind of customers. Corporate communication is a vital marketing tool and if it is properly managed, it brings about positive customer perception. An organization that communicate their corporate identity properly, customers are likely to perceive a positive mental picture of the company. Again, any change in corporate identity can affect the perception customers have about the organization. When hotel personnel perceive the organization to be unique and distinctive in their responsibilities and care towards them, they tend to treat the customers well, thereby positions the firm positively in the mind of the customers. This therefore entails that corporate reputation and communication are veritable marketing techniques to improve marketing effectiveness and organisational performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made available for banks to implement:

- i. For 4-star hotels to maintain their identity, management are encouraged to design and implement services that are appealing to stakeholders and the public. This will bring about stakeholders' endorsement and reputation for the banks.
- ii. To enhance organisational performance, management of 4-star hotels are expected to disseminate vital information about the organization's corporate existence and value propositions on one hand, and to also coordinate inter-departmental flow of information in order to ensure that the corporate marketing strategies are understood and implemented by every employee of the organization.

Constantly communicating and engaging with relevant customers on products and services have been confirmed by this research to be key in commanding customer loyalty. Therefore, strategists of banks should use strategic avenues or channels to interact with customers as they seek to promote the brand and sale it to the relevant publics.

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